

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6386804>

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Annotation: *The English language is one of the most widespread languages in the world. As a result, there is always a need for people to be able to use the language efficiently. To get proficiency in the English language, one must make an effort to learn the four major skills of the language. Learning languages is a continuous process, where teaching techniques and methods play a crucial role in developing the student's practical knowledge. The article deals with the various innovative and the most effective methods of teaching English as a second language, which can be suitable for learners of all ages.*

Keywords: *Innovative methods, practical skills, techniques, communication skills, CLT, activities, language learning process, the direct method, The Audio Lingual Method (ALM), authentic materials, CALL.*

Millions of people nowadays desire to enhance their command of English or ensure that their children do as well. And possibilities to learn English are available in a variety of settings, including official education, travel, study abroad, media, and the Internet. The global demand for English has resulted in a huge need for quality language education as well as language teaching tools and resources. Learners establish challenging goals for themselves. The main function of teachers is to provide the learners with the contemporary methods of acquiring the language in faster and most effective ways. Nowadays we utterly need to remove the traditional methods and shed a light on modern student-centered approaches, which will give unimaginable results in the future. Modern pedagogical technologies propose altering the educational situation so that the teacher, rather than being an "indisputable authority," becomes an attentive and interested companion and a partner in the learning phase.

The Communicative Method of Teaching English. Throughout the twentieth century, communicative language education has been one of the most effective and widely used techniques of teaching a second language. In the early 1970s, the concept of communicative language education emerged in the United Kingdom. British linguists studied the value of communicative language education rather than grammatical, lexical, and phonological norms in the late 1960s. The main objectives of CLT (Communicative language technique) are:

- to enhance the communicative proficiency of all skills like listening, reading, speaking, and writing;
- to focus on fluency of the language rather than the accuracy of the grammar;
- to enable learners to participate in the natural environment, such as group and pair work, and so on;
- to use authentic materials, which should be similar to the classroom activities and real-world;
- to create a more interactive environment for language learners.

The Direct Method. The Direct method was proposed by the innovators and reformers of the 19 century. In this method, all instruction is given in the target language, motivating the learner to think in that language. Using mother tongue and practicing the translation methods are not allowed there. The teacher teaches the grammar rules through the various inductive methods. It means that, by practicing the language, students discover grammatical rules on their own. The goal for pupils is to make links between their experiences and their language. They accomplish this by emphasizing proper pronunciation and the improvement of oral skills.

The main functions of this method:

SHOW. The students learn new words with the assistance of visual aids, flashcards. The teacher uses body language to explain the words.

SAY. The teacher verbally presents the words to pay attention to their pronunciation.

TRY. The learners should repeat after the teacher.

CORRECT. The teacher ensures to check the learner's correct pronunciation.

REPEAT. The learners repeat the words several times.

The Audio Lingual Method. The Audio Lingual Method is a foreign language teaching method that prioritizes listening and speaking before reading and writing. It predominantly involves dialogues as the primary mode of language teaching and drills as the primary training technique. According to the audio-lingual method, pupils should be taught a language directly, without utilizing their home language to explain new terms or grammar in the target language. The Audio Lingual Method (ALM) was developed in the 1940s in the United States of America (USA). Even though the method is regarded as quite old, many language teachers appreciate it and believe it is a helpful technique.

There is some characteristic of the Audio Lingual Method :

- Language learning is habit-formation;
- Language skills are learned more effectively if they are presented orally first, then in written form;
- Analogy is a better foundation for language learning than analysis;
- The meaning of words can be taught only in a linguistic and cultural context.

The role of ICT in teaching the English Language. Currently, ICT(Information and Communication Technology) has been used in every field of life, including education. ICT in education has just recently started to appeal to the potential and considerable improvements in language learning. It has become a serious concern in the education system, and it has been applied from preschool to university to assist students and teachers in the teaching and learning process. Computers play a crucial role in teaching and learning foreign languages, students and teachers can benefit, sharpen their language skills while appropriately using them. The necessity of technical education has resulted in a communication revolution as well as the rapid growth of technological applications in teaching and learning. The latest method that is developing is CALL (Computer Assisted Language Learning). Some language learning specialists and practitioners strongly promote the use of ICT in language learning to improve the quality and efficiency of learning, which can ensure the effectiveness of knowledge and mastery of the language studied. In other words, the integration of ICT in the field of language learning is unavoidable since ICT and language learning are two features that complement each other like two sides of the same coin (Hartoyo, 2010). The tool is flexible and interactive in terms of time and place, furthermore, it is admitted more than other media can encourage students in language learning due to the diverse ways of conducting the lessons with interactive methods. Therefore, CALL can stimulate interaction and develop communicative ability by delivering authentic content to the class or self-learning. The best examples for authentic materials can be e-books, magazines, various films in the English language, software messengers for speaking, a multitude number of apps for enhancing and checking language skills.

Conclusion: Teaching a foreign language is one of the most difficult but rewarding jobs; the teacher is responsible for making the lessons more engaging and effective and evoking the learners' interest. The key objective of the approaches stated above is to conduct the classes in an approachable manner based on the learner's type, to show them a new world of language culture through authentic resources, and, most significantly, to motivate them to self-study and communicate in the target language.

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